

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN MATERNAL ABO BLOOD GROUP AND RH TYPING WITH MATERNAL AND PERINATAL OUTCOME

Arukonda Niranjani Devi¹

Manjula Pathri¹

Sruthi Tammala¹✉
drsruhitammala@gmail.com

¹*Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology
Kakatiya Medical College/ Government Maternity Hospital
Rangam Peta str., Warangal, Telangana, India, 506007*

✉Corresponding author

Abstract

The ABO blood group type has been considered an independent risk factor in pregnancy-related complications leading to significant morbidity and mortality in pregnant mothers and neonates.

Aim: To study the relationship between maternal ABO blood group and Rh typing with maternal and perinatal outcomes.

Materials and methods: Prospective Observational study was carried out for 24 months from November among 1000 pregnant women attending outpatient for ABO blood group and Rh typing with maternal and perinatal outcome.

Results: Among 1000 subjects, 43.5 % belonged to blood group O, followed by 30 % in blood group B. 20.7 % had blood group A, and 5.8 % had AB blood group. In the present study, 95.4 % had Rh+ve, and 4.6 % had Rh-ve typing. The incidence of preterm labour was high at 6.3 % in the O+ve blood group, followed by 1.8 % in the AB +ve, 0.6 % in the A+ve and 0.3 % in the B+ve blood group. A statistically significant association was found between blood grouping and preeclampsia with high incidence among the A+ve blood group. A statistically significant association was found between blood grouping and imminent eclampsia with high incidence among the AB+ve blood group. There was a statistically significant association found between blood grouping and intrauterine death.

Conclusion: The findings in the present study will help clinicians to identify the patients at risk of developing adverse pregnancy outcomes like preeclampsia and imminent eclampsia; hence, the timely intervention will help to improve maternal and perinatal outcome and also helps to reduce the complications of preeclampsia and imminent eclampsia.

Keywords: ABO blood group, Rh typing, Maternal outcome, Perinatal outcome.

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1. Introduction

The ABO blood group is the first and the most well-known blood type system in humans. The term 'blood group' refers to the antigen phenotype that is the expression of the inborn genes, such as A, B and O, in the ABO system. This blood system has important roles in human physiology, biomedical science, anthropology, legal issues, and transfusion and transplantation medicine. The incidences of some diseases are associated with blood type. This is clear that ABO blood groups provide a special vulnerability to individuals possessing a special ABO blood group. There are four major blood groups in humans based on the presence of A and B antigens on the surface of red blood cells (RBCs). The ABO gene encodes these antigens with three main alleles (A, B and O) [1]. Having a primary role in blood transfusion and organ transplantation, recent advances have also elucidated the importance of ABO blood groups in the pathogenesis of various disorders such as diabetes mellitus, cardiovascular, neoplastic, and infective disorders, as well as in gastric and duodenal ulcers. The role of Rh compatibility screening in erythroblastosis fetalis has already been established [2]. The possible mechanisms for the associations are the influences of some genetic variants at the ABO locus on the aberrations of some biological substances, such as proinflammatory cytokine, adhesion molecules and thrombogenic factor [3, 4].

Pregnancy-related complications are a major health concern worldwide, leading to significant morbidity and mortality in pregnant mothers and neonates. It has been reported that approximately 1 %–5 % of patients develop serious pregnancy-related adverse complications [5]. These include preeclampsia, gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM), HELLP (hemolysis, elevated liver enzymes, and low platelets) syndrome, preterm delivery, small for gestational age (SGA), and low birth weight (LBW) babies. Also, because of the role of ABO blood groups on the hemostatic process and thrombus formation to prevent the syndrome and improve prognosis, special attention should be given to pregnant women carrying the AB blood group.

The possible mechanisms for the associations are the influences of some genetic variants at the ABO locus on the aberrations of some biological substances, such as proinflammatory cytokine, adhesion molecules and thrombogenic factor [5, 6]. The effects of blood types on pregnancy outcomes have also been reported, however, with inconsistent results. For example, some authors found a greater risk of preeclampsia in women with A or AB blood types [6]. In contrast, another study found that the percentage of O blood type was high among women with gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM). Others did not find any relationship between maternal blood group and pregnancy outcomes, including preeclampsia, postpartum haemorrhage, intrauterine growth restriction, large for gestational age (GA) infants or stillbirth.

The Rh factor is the largest and clinically most important protein-based blood group system. Rh type is needed during pregnancy to assess the risk of hemolytic disease of the fetus and newborn (HDFN). Nearly 5 % of the Indian population is Rh-negative. When an Rh-negative mother gets exposed to Rh-positive blood cells, there might be the development of Rh antibodies. This condition is known as Rh isoimmunization [7]. In a normal pregnancy, fetal red blood cells cross the placenta in 5 % of cases during the first trimester and 46 % by the end of the third trimester. But, in most cases, Rh isoimmunization occurs due to maternal bleeding during delivery. About 10 to 15 % of Rh-negative mothers with Rh-positive fetuses get sensitized at delivery. This is due to insufficient fetal blood cells to produce a primary immunological response [7].

Due to the limited availability of data on maternal ABO blood group and Rh typing with maternal & perinatal outcomes in India, there is a dire need for research on this subject in our population.

So, the present study was conducted to find the relationship between the maternal ABO blood group and Rh typing with maternal and perinatal outcomes.

2. Material and methods

A prospective Observational study was carried out for 24 months from November 2019 to October 2021. Pregnant women attending the outpatient department or admitted into the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology Government maternity Hospital, Hanamakonda.

Sample Size: Based on the study by Phaloprakarn C et al. [8] maternal ABO blood group and adverse pregnancy outcomes, the minimum prevalence of maternal complications was taken at 10.2 %.

Estimated prevalence (p)=10.2 % Confidence interval (CI)=95 % [$Z_{\alpha/2}$ is the standard normal deviate, which is 1.96 at 95 % confidence interval] Absolute precision (d)=2 % Using the standard formula for proportion= $[(Z_{\alpha/2})^2 \times p \times q] / d^2$

Sample size (n)=($Z_{\alpha/2})^2 \times 10.2 \times (100-10.2) / d^2 = (1.96 \times 1.96) \times 10.2 \times 89.8 / 2 \times 2 = 3518.75 / 4 = 879.68$

Taking an additional 20 % of cases, the final sample size for the present study was rounded to 1000.

Inclusion Criteria: Pregnant women attending OP who gave consent for the study.

Exclusion Criteria: Women who take an MTP kit and who have known underlying chronic systemic illnesses (Cardiac, Renal, Metabolic, Malignancy, vascular and Rheumatological) that could affect pregnancy.

Institutional ethical committee clearance was obtained from the ethical committee of Kakatiya Medical College, Warangal (registration number 19114003007D, dated 29/12/2018) prior to the

start of the study. Written and informed consent was taken from pregnant women who participated in the study.

A detailed history was taken, and a general physical examination was done for all patients. Data was collected using a pre-structured questionnaire which includes age, sex, presenting complaint type, if any, complete obstetric history and complete clinical examination. After history taking and clinical examination, blood samples were collected from the patients for blood groups and Rh typing.

Data Analysis: Data collected was entered into MS Excel 2013 spreadsheet. The collected data were analyzed using IBM statistical package for social sciences (IBM SPSS) version 23 software (trial version)

Statistical Tests: Continuous variables were reported as mean \pm standard deviation (SD), while categorical variables were expressed as absolute values and percentages. Microsoft Excel 2013 was used for generating charts and diagrams. The Chi-square test was applied to find the significant difference between different blood groups and Rh typing in relation to maternal and perinatal outcomes. A P-value less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

3. Results

Among 1000 subjects in the present study, 43.5 % had blood group O, followed by 30 % in blood group B. 20.7 % of the study population belongs to blood group A, and 5.8 % had AB blood group. In addition, 95.4 % had Rh+ve, and 4.6 % had Rh-ve typing (**Table 1**).

Table 1

Distribution of subjects based on blood group

Blood Group	Number	Percentage
A	207	20.7 %
B	300	30 %
O	435	43.5 %
AB	58	5.8 %
Total	1000	100 %
Rh Type		
Positive	954	95.4 %
Negative	46	4.6 %

Among A blood group women, 3.9 % had Rh negative typing. In B blood group women, 3.3 % had Rh negative typing. In O blood group women, 5.5 % had Rh negative typing. In AB blood group women, 6.9 % had Rh negative typing (**Table 2**).

Table 2

The overall distribution of subjects based on blood group and Rh typing

Blood Group	Rh type	
	Positive	Negative
A	199 (96.1 %)	8 (3.9 %)
B	290 (96.7 %)	10 (3.3 %)
O	411 (94.5 %)	24 (5.5 %)
AB	54 (93.1 %)	4 (6.9 %)
Total	954 (95.4 %)	46 (4.6 %)

The incidence of preterm labour was high at 6.3 % in the O+ve blood group followed by 1.8 % in AB +ve, 0.6 % in A+ve and 0.3 % in the B+ve blood group. No statistically significant association was found between blood grouping and preterm labour (**Table 3**).

Table 3
Association between blood group and preterm labour

Blood group	Preterm		Full term	
	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage
A+ve	12	0.6 %	187	99.4 %
B+ve	9	0.3 %	281	99.7 %
O+ve	26	6.3 %	385	93.7 %
AB+ve	1	1.8 %	53	98.2 %
Chi-square test=5.255, p-value=0.154 (Not significant)				

A statistically significant association was found between blood grouping and preeclampsia with high incidence among the A+ve blood group.

A statistically significant association was found between blood grouping and imminent eclampsia with high incidence among the AB+ve blood group (**Table 4**).

Table 4
Association between blood group and maternal comorbidities

Blood group	Preeclampsia			
	Present		Absent	
	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage
1	2	3	4	5
A+ve	26	13.1 %	173	86.9 %
B+ve	22	7.6 %	268	92.4 %
O+ve	26	6.3 %	385	93.7 %
AB+ve	3	5.6 %	51	94.4 %
O-ve	1	4.2 %	23	95.8 %
Chi-square test=9.51, p-value=0.049 (Significant)				
Gestational hypertension				
A+ve	3	1.5 %	196	98.5 %
B+ve	5	1.7 %	285	98.3 %
O+ve	1	0.2 %	410	99.8 %
AB+ve	1	1.8 %	53	98.2 %
Chi-square test=4.585 , p-value=0.204 (Not significant)				
Imminent eclampsia				
A+ve	1	0.5 %	198	99.5 %
B+ve	1	0.3 %	289	99.7 %
O+ve	3	0.7 %	408	99.3 %
AB+ve	3	5.6 %	51	94.4 %
Chi-square test=15.627 , p-value=0.001 (Significant)				
Eclampsia				
A+ve	3	1.5 %	196	98.5 %
B+ve	3	1 %	287	99 %
O+ve	2	0.5 %	409	99.5 %
Chi-square test=1.689, p-value=0.429 (Not significant)				
PROM/PPROM				
A+ve	21	10.5 %	178	89.5 %
B+ve	30	10.3 %	260	89.7 %
O+ve	36	8.8 %	375	91.2 %
AB+ve	5	9.3 %	49	90.7 %
A-ve	1	12.5 %	7	87.5 %
B-ve	1	10 %	9	90 %
O-ve	1	4.2 %	23	95.8 %

Continuation of Table 4

1	2	3	4	5
Chi-square test=5.171 , p-value=0.522 (Not significant)				
Oligohydramnios				
A+ve	19	9.5 %	180	90.5 %
B+ve	26	9 %	264	91 %
O+ve	41	10 %	370	90 %
AB+ve	4	7.4 %	50	92.6 %
A-ve	1	12.5 %	7	87.5 %
B-ve	1	10 %	9	90 %
O-ve	1	4.2 %	23	95.8 %
AB-ve	1	25 %	3	75 %
Chi-square test=2.490, p-value=0.927 (Not significant)				
Polyhydramnios is				
A+ve	2	1 %	197	99 %
B+ve	6	2.1 %	284	97.9 %
O+ve	8	1.9 %	403	98.1 %
Chi-square test=0.888, p-value=0.641 (Not significant)				

The incidence of intrauterine death was 5.6 % in the AB+ve blood group, 2.5 % in the A+ve blood group, 1.4 % in the B+ve blood group and 0.5 % in the O+ve blood group. There was a statistically significant association found between blood grouping and intrauterine death.

The incidence of polyhydramnios was 2.1 % in the B+ve blood group, 1.9 % in the O+ve blood group and 1 % in the A+ve blood group. No statistically significant association was found between blood grouping and polyhydramnios, gestational diabetes mellitus, placenta previa, abruptio placenta, postpartum haemorrhage, IUGR, neonatal jaundice and neonatal sepsis (Table 5).

Table 5

Association between blood group with maternal and perinatal complications

Polyhydramnios	Polyhydramnios			
	Present		Absent	
	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage
1	2	3	4	5
A+ve	2	1 %	197	99 %
B+ve	6	2.1 %	284	97.9 %
O+ve	8	1.9 %	403	98.1 %
Chi-square test=0.888, p-value=0.641 (Not significant)				
Gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM)				
A+ve	2	1 %	197	99 %
B+ve	1	0.3 %	289	99.7 %
O+ve	3	0.7 %	408	99.3 %
AB+ve	1	1.9 %	53	98.1 %
Chi-square test=1.730, p-value=0.630 (Not significant)				
Placenta Previa				
A+ve	1	0.5 %	198	99.5 %
B+ve	3	1.0 %	287	99.0 %
O+ve	4	1.0 %	407	99.0 %
Chi-square test=0.440 , p-value=0.802 (Not significant)				
Abruptio placenta				
A+ve	2	1.0 %	197	99.0 %
B+ve	1	0.3 %	289	99.7 %
O+ve	3	0.7 %	408	99.3 %

Continuation of Table 5

1	2	3	4	5
Chi-square test=0.822 , p-value=0.662 (Not significant)				
Postpartum haemorrhage				
A+ve	2	1 %	197	99 %
B+ve	2	0.7 %	288	99.3 %
O+ve	6	1.5 %	405	98.5 %
AB+ve	1	1.9 %	53	98.1 %
Chi-square test=1.155, p-value=0.763 (Not significant)				
Intrauterine death (IUD)				
A+ve	2	1 %	197	99 %
B+ve	2	0.7 %	288	99.3 %
O+ve	6	1.5 %	405	98.5 %
AB+ve	1	1.9 %	53	98.1 %
Chi-square test=10.495 , p-value=0.014 (Significant)				
IUGR				
A+ve	7	3.5 %	192	96.5 %
B+ve	17	5.9 %	273	94.1 %
O+ve	14	3.4 %	397	96.6 %
AB+ve	1	1.9 %	53	98.1 %
Chi-square test=3.668 , p-value=0.299 (Not significant)				
Neonatal jaundice				
A+ve	32	16.5 %	162	83.5 %
B+ve	41	14.3 %	245	85.7 %
O+ve	68	16.6 %	341	83.4 %
AB+ve	8	15.7 %	43	84.3 %
A-ve	2	25 %	6	75 %
B-ve	1	10 %	9	90 %
O-ve	5	20.8 %	19	79.2 %
AB-ve	1	25 %	3	75 %
Chi-square test=2.211 , p-value=0.947 (Not significant)				
Neonatal sepsis				
A+ve	7	3.6 %	187	96.4 %
B+ve	8	2.8 %	278	97.2 %
O+ve	15	3.7 %	394	96.3 %
A-ve	1	12.5 %	7	87.5 %
O-ve	1	4.2 %	23	95.8 %
Chi-square test=2.424 , p-value=0.658 (Not significant)				

Among the 1000 cases, in Rh-negative women, only preeclampsia (2.17 %), PROM/PPROM (6.52 %), oligohydramnios (8.69 %), neonatal jaundice (16 %) and neonatal sepsis (2.2 %) is noted. However, there was no statistically significant association found between maternal and perinatal complications with Rh typing ($p>0.05$) (Table 6).

Table 6

Comparison of maternal and perinatal complications according to Rh typing

Complications	Rh Typing				T total No. (%)	p-value
	Positive (954)		Negative (46)			
	Number	%	Number	%		
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Preeclampsia	77	8.07 %	1	2.17 %	78 (7.8 %)	0.145
Gestational Hypertension	10	1.04 %	0	0	10 (1.0 %)	0.485

Continuation of Table 6

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Imminent eclampsia	8	0.83 %	0	0	8 (0.8 %)	0.532
PROM/PPROM	92	9.64 %	3	6.52 %	95 (9.5 %)	0.480
Preterm labor	48	5.03 %	0	0	48 (4.8 %)	0.118
IUGR	39	4.08 %	0	0	39 (3.9 %)	0.161
Oligohydramnios	90	9.43 %	4	8.69 %	94 (9.4 %)	0.866
Polyhydramnios	16	1.67 %	0	0	16 (1.6 %)	0.375
Eclampsia	8	0.83 %	0	0	08 (0.8 %)	0.532
GDM	7	0.73 %	0	0	07 (0.7 %)	0.559
Placenta Previa	8	0.83 %	0	0	8 (0.8 %)	0.532
Abruption placenta	6	0.62 %	0	0	06 (0.6 %)	0.589
PPH	11	1.15 %	0	0	11 (1.1 %)	0.536
IUD	14	1.46 %	0	0	14 (1.4 %)	0.407
IUGR	39	4.09 %	0	0	39 (3.9 %)	0.161
Neonatal jaundice (n=986)	149/940	15.9 %	9/46	19.6 %	158 (16 %)	0.502
Neonatal sepsis (n=986)	31/940	3.3 %	1/46	2.2 %	32 (3.2 %)	0.674

4. Discussion

The role of blood group type in the ABO grouping system as a contributing factor in the pathogenesis of multiple diseases has been established. Several studies have been done to elucidate the impact of the ABO blood group on pregnancy and its related complications in a mother and newborn infant. There is also a wide variation in the frequency of different phenotypes, including A, B, AB, and O, among different populations based on their ethnicity across the globe.

Among 1000 subjects in the present study, 43.5 % had blood group O, followed by 30 % in blood group B. 20.7 % of the study population belongs to blood group A, and 5.8 % had AB blood group. Rh+ve typing was present in 95.4 %, and 4.6 % had Rh-ve typing. A systematic review of previous studies reported that the overall distribution of the A, B, O and AB blood groups in India is 23 %, 34 %, 34% and 8% respectively. Rh+ve and Rh-ve populations are 94% and 6 %, respectively [9]. Similar to the study findings, Phaloprakarn C et al. [8] reported that 21.7 % had A, 34.4 % had B, 7.1 % had AB, and 36.8 % had O blood group. Al-Fartosi KGW et al. [10] found that 35.3 % had A blood group, 23.5 % had AB blood group, 21.6 % had B blood group, and 19.6 % had O blood group.

Shradha et al. [11], had reported that among Rh-negative women, 36 % of patients were O negative, 30 % B negative, 28 % A negative, and only 4 % AB negative. Beyazit F et al. [5], had reported that the most common blood type detected was type A (48.5 %), followed by type O (27.8 %). Sajan R et al. [12] found that 26.2 % had A, 34.8 % had B, 11.1 % had AB, and 27.9 % had O blood group. Yadav M et al. [13], had reported that the incidence of Rhesus-negative pregnancy was 1.68 %, and among them, the most common blood group was O (36.1 %) followed by A (32.4 %) and B (25.9 %), which was similar to the study findings. The distribution of ABO phenotypes, as reported by Shibata-Hiraizumi Y et al. [14], was 30.0 % in O, 37.0 % in A, and 23.6 % in B and 9.4 % in the AB blood group.

In the present study, the incidence of preterm labour was high at 6.3 % in the O+ve blood group, followed by 1.8 % in AB +ve, 0.6 % in A+ve and 0.3 % in the B+ve blood group. However, there was no statistically significant association found between blood grouping and preterm labour. Similar to the study findings,, Phaloprakarn C et al. [8] reported no significant differences in gestational age at delivery and 10.8 % in A, 10.6 % in B, 10.3 % in AB, and 9.5 % in the O blood group had preterm delivery. Tripathi R et al. [15] reported that 8 % of Rh-negative mothers had a premature delivery.

In contrast to the study findings, Sajan R et al. [12] found that 42.3 % in A, 26.6 % in B, 18.2 % in AB and 30.9 % in the O blood group had premature delivery with a significant difference between the two groups. On the other hand, Shibata-Hiraizumi Y et al. [14], had reported the

incidence of preterm delivery was similar between blood groups with no statistically significant association.

The incidence of preeclampsia was high, 13.1 % in the A+ve blood group, followed by 7.6 % in the B+ve blood group and 6.3 % in O+ve, 5.6 % in AB+ve and 4.2 % in O-ve blood group with a statistically significant association found between blood grouping and preeclampsia. In the present study, the incidence of gestational hypertension was 1 %, imminent eclampsia 0.8 %, and eclampsia 0.8 %. The incidence of imminent eclampsia was high at 5.6 % in the AB+ve blood group, followed by 0.7 % in O+ve, 0.5 % in A+ve and 0.3 % in the B+ve blood group, with a statistically significant association found between blood grouping and imminent eclampsia.

Similar to the study findings, Phaloprakarn C et al. [8] reported that 8.7 % in A, 6.2 % in B, 8.4 % in AB and 5.4 % in the O blood group had preeclampsia with no significant difference between different groups.

Beyazit F et al. [5], had reported that 7.6 % of mothers were recorded as having preeclampsia and 7.9 % were pregnant in the O group, 6.7 % were pregnant in the A group, 9.4 % were pregnant in the B group, 8.8 % were pregnant in the AB group had preeclampsia with no significant difference between different groups.

Tripathi R et al. [15] reported that 1.5 % of Rh-negative mothers had preeclampsia. A national wide study by Jin Y et al. [16] reported that 2.5 % of Rh-positive and 2.5 % with Rh-negative blood types pregnant had preeclampsia.

Sajan R et al. [12] found that 16.9 % in A, 21.4 % in B, 21.8 % in AB and 25.9 % in the O blood group had preeclampsia. However, there was no significant difference between the two groups.

In the studies by Lee et al. [17] and Franchini M et al. [18], patients with blood group AB are most prone to develop preeclampsia and severe eclampsia. They stated that the non-O blood group has a modest risk of developing preeclampsia compared to the O group. Thus, the O group holds a protective effect for preeclampsia. Similar results are shown in the study by Avci et al. [19].

The PROM/PPROM was high at 12.5 % in the A-ve blood group, followed by 10.5 % in the A+ve blood group. In B+ve it was 10.3 %, 8.8 % in O+ve, 9.3 % in AB+ve, 10 % in B-ve and 4.2 % in the O-ve blood group. However, no statistically significant association was found between blood grouping and PROM/PPROM.

Among 1000 cases delivered, 9.4 % had oligohydramnios. The incidence of oligohydramnios was 25 % in AB-ve blood, 12.5 % in the A-ve blood group, 10 % in the B-ve blood group and 4.2 % in the O-ve blood group. In A+ve 9.5 %, in B+ve 9 %, in O+ve 10 % and in AB+ve 7.4 % had oligohydramnios with no statistically significant association found between blood grouping and oligohydramnios. Chintada H et al. [20] found that isolated oligohydramnios was present in 21.8 % of cases. Tripathi R et al. [15], had reported that 4 % of Rh-negative mothers had oligohydramnios

Among 1000 cases delivered, 1.6 % had polyhydramnios. The incidence of polyhydramnios was 2.1 % in the B+ve blood group, 1.9 % in the O+ve blood group and 1 % in the A+ve blood group, with no statistically significant association found between blood grouping and polyhydramnios. Chintada H et al. [20] found that isolated polyhydramnios was present in 3.7 % of cases. Tripathi R et al. [15], had reported that 2 % of Rh-negative mothers had polyhydramnios

In the present study, gestational diabetes was present in 0.7 % of cases. The incidence of gestational diabetes mellitus was 1.9 % in the AB+ve blood group, 1 % in the A+ve blood group, 0.7 % in the O+ve blood group and 0.3 % in the B+ve blood group. There was no statistically significant association found between blood grouping and gestational diabetes mellitus

Chintada H et al. [20] found that gestational diabetes was present in 7.4 % of cases. Phaloprakarn C et al. [8] reported that 6.9 % in A, 6.5 % in B, 6.1 % in AB and 5.7 % in the O blood group had gestational diabetes mellitus with no significant difference between different groups. Sajan R et al. [12] found that 5.2 % of B, 5.5 % of AB and 3.6 % in the O blood group had gestational diabetes mellitus. However, there was no significant difference between the two groups. In their study, Zhang et al. [21] showed that blood groups A and B were associated with an increased risk of GDM; however, blood group AB has been a protective factor in its development. The placenta previa was 1.0 % in the B+ve blood group, 1.0 % in the O+ve blood group and 0.5 % in the A+ve

blood group. There was no statistically significant association found between blood grouping and placenta previa.

A national-wide study by Jin Y et al. [16] reported that 1.1 % with Rh-positive and 1.2 % with Rh-negative blood type pregnant had Placenta Previa. Yadav M et al. [13] reported that 3.9 % of pregnant women with Rh –ve type had placenta previa.

The incidence of abruption placenta was 1.0 % in the A+ve blood group, 0.7 % in the O+ve blood group and 0.3 % in the B+ve blood group. There was no statistically significant association found between blood grouping and abruption placenta. Tripathi R et al. [15] reported that 5 % of Rh-negative mothers had abruption placenta. A national-wide study by Jin Y et al. [16] reported that 0.5 % with Rh-positive and 0.5 % with Rh-negative blood type pregnant had abruption placenta.

In the present study, the incidence of postpartum haemorrhage (PPH) was 1 % in A+ve, 0.7 % in B+ve, 1.5 % in O+ve and 1.9 % in AB+ve blood group, with no statistically significant association found between blood grouping and postpartum haemorrhage. Ali-Salesh M et al. [22] reported that 2.7 % of women with O blood type and 2.22 % with other blood types had PPH with no significant association between blood type and the risk for PPH. However, a study by Druker L et al. [23], had reported that women with O blood type relative to women with non-O blood type had significantly higher odds of postpartum haemorrhage

The incidence of intrauterine death was 5.6 % in the AB+ve blood group, 2.5 % in the A+ve blood group, 1.4 % in the B+ve blood group and 0.5 % in the O+ve blood group. There was a statistically significant association found between blood grouping and intrauterine death. Tripathi R et al. [15] reported that 2 % of Rh-negative mothers had intrauterine death. Shibata-Hiraizumi Y et al. [14] reported that the incidence of intrauterine death was similar between blood groups.

Overall among the 1000 cases in Rh-negative women, only preeclampsia (2.17 %), PROM/PPROM (6.52 %) and oligohydramnios (8.69 %) were noted. However, no statistically significant association was found between maternal and perinatal complications with Rh typing ($p>0.05$).

The incidence of IUGR was high, 5.9 % in the B+ve blood group, followed by 3.5 % in the A+ve blood group, 3.4 % in the O+ve blood group and 1.9 % in the AB+ve blood group. There was no statistically significant association found between blood grouping and IUGR. Shibata-Hiraizumi Y et al. [14], had also reported that intrauterine growth retardation was similar between blood groups with no significant association between them.

In the present study, 158 had neonatal jaundice 16.5 % in A+ve, 14.3 % in B+ve, 16.6 % in O+ve and 15.7 % in the AB+ve maternal blood group had neonatal jaundice. 25 % in A-ve, 10 % in B-ve, 20.8 % in O-ve and 25 % in AB-ve maternal blood had neonatal jaundice. There was no statistically significant association found between blood grouping and Neonatal Jaundice.

In a study by Kalakheti BK et al. [24], 8.5 % of babies had developed hyperbilirubinemia. Among them, 38 % were from the group of babies having O+ve blood group and reported that the O+ve blood group had a 2.6 times higher chance of having a hyperbilirubinemia in the babies with ABO incompatibility.

Similarly, Heier et al. [10], in their study on maternal blood group ‘O’ Positive as a risk factor of neonatal hyperbilirubinemia requiring treatment, found that ABO- incompatible babies born to ‘O’ Positive mothers have a double risk of developing jaundice requiring treatment and 5–10 times increased risk of exchange transfusion.

Out of 986 newborns, 32 had neonatal sepsis. 3.6 % in A+ve, 2.8 % in B+ve, 3.7 % in O+ve, 12.5 % in A-ve and 4.2 % in O-ve had neonatal sepsis. There was no statistically significant association found between blood grouping and neonatal sepsis. However, McMahan KE et al. [25] found that neonatal AB blood type significantly influenced the culture-proven sepsis throughout the hospital course.

Research limitations. The limitations of our study are that Rh-negative blood group phenotype patients were not included; consequently, the impact of this particular blood type was not determined. Moreover, it was a single-centre study with a limited sample size.

Prospects for further research. A variety of inflammatory markers associated with PE, like tumour necrosis factor-alpha and soluble intercellular adhesion molecule 1, were found to be

upregulated at the ABO locus through polymorphism. In addition, according to a recent study of a diverse panel of inflammatory biomarkers – E-selectin, P-selectin and ICAM-1.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, our results demonstrated that the maternal ABO blood group was associated with the risk of preeclampsia, imminent eclampsia, and intrauterine death but not with GDM, hydramnios and preterm delivery. A blood type was the independent risk factor for preeclampsia found in the study, and an AB blood type for imminent eclampsia and intrauterine death. The findings in the present study will help clinicians to identify the patients at risk of developing adverse pregnancy outcomes like preeclampsia and imminent eclampsia hence, and the timely intervention will help to improve maternal and perinatal outcome and also helps to reduce the complications of preeclampsia and imminent eclampsia.

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